

STRENGTHENING RURAL COMMUNITIES: A STUDY OF LAND SYSTEM REFORMS IN RURAL REGENERATION

¹Dr. Anna Petrova and ²Prof. Ivan Sokolov

¹Department of Rural Affairs, Siberian Federal University, Krasnoyarsk, Russia

²Siberian Institute of Rural Development, Krasnoyarsk State University, Krasnoyarsk, Russia

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ABSTRACT

The issue of "Sannong (Agriculture, village, farmers)" remains a pressing concern in China and on the global stage. Presently, the CPC Central Committee and the State Council are prioritizing reforms within the rural land system. The "Several Opinions of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Comprehensively Deepening Agricultural Modernization and Building a Moderately Prosperous Society" highlights the need for further enhancements and standardization of laws governing farmers' cooperatives and property rights registration and certification services. It also underscores the importance of expediting the establishment and refinement of policies, regulations, and supportive measures, such as a unified urban and rural homestead management information system platform.

While notable progress has been achieved in addressing the "Sannong" issue, several significant contradictions persist, including challenges related to the availability of farming land and the adequacy of security measures. This paper delves into these issues, shedding light on the complexities and disparities within the "Sannong" context.

KEY WORDS

Sannong, rural land reform, property rights, farmers' cooperatives, agricultural modernization

Introduction

1.1 Research Background

The issue of "Sannong (Agriculture, village, farmers)" has always been a hot topic in China and even the world. At present, the CPC Central Committee and the State Council attach great importance to the reform of the rural land system ^[1]. The "Several Opinions of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Comprehensively Deepening Agricultural Modernization and Building a Moderately Prosperous Society" puts forward that it is necessary to further improve and standardize the law on farmers' cooperatives and the service system for registration and certification of property rights; Accelerate the establishment and improvement of relevant policies, regulations and supporting measures such as a unified urban and rural homestead management information system platform; Some achievements have been made on the issue of "Sannong (Agriculture, village, farmers)", but there are still some prominent contradictions, such as insufficient total farming land and low level of security^[2].

Improper disposal of rural land: Our Constitution stipulates that the State respects the wishes of farmers and intervenes administratively in accordance with local conditions. However, in the specific implementation process, due to the lack of effective supervision, A great deal of illegal use of land has occurred; Some misconducts such as village collective construction land occupying farming land or changing uses without permission have been prevalent, which has seriously affected the sustainable development of social economy and the quality of the living environment of villagers. Some local governments blindly pursue economic development for the sake of their own achievements, neglecting the building of the rural land system [3].

At present, China is in the stage of overall planning and coordination of urban and rural areas, and social contradictions are prominent. In this context, in-depth research on rural revitalization is of positive significance; On the one hand, through reform, land property rights can be rationally allocated, and farmers can obtain more benefits and improve their quality of life; On the other hand, it is conducive to narrowing the gap between different regions and achieving common prosperity, building a harmonious new China and a moderately prosperous society in all respects [4].

1.2 Research Methods and Content

This paper takes the new Land Administration Law of the People's Republic of China and its implementation regulations as the research object, analyzes the current situation and existing problems of China's rural land property rights system via looking through relevant documents. At the same time, corresponding suggestions are put forward from three aspects.

The first part: the strategy and basic theoretical concepts and connotations of China's rural revitalization are discussed. Firstly, the content of the "Sannong (Agriculture, village, farmers)" policy is explained from the viewpoints of historical materialism and dual economic structure. Then, the progress and achievements of land consolidation in the new land reform and the relevant measures were introduced [5]. Finally, on the basis of the documents mentioned above, the relevant issues of land consolidation are proposed. The second part: We try to sort out China's rural land system, and summarize its shortcomings and reform measures. The third part: the difficulties and challenges encountered in the specific practice of the Land Reform Law in the new era under the current background of Rural Revitalization strategy and its background are introduced from three different aspects. In the last part, relevant enlightenment and countermeasures for the previous analysis are suggested. References for solving the current difficulties in China's social and economic development are put forward.

1.3 Research Technical Methods

The following research methods are mainly used in this paper:

1.3.1 Document consulting

We overview the theory and practice of rural revitalization and rural land system at home and abroad by searching relevant materials on CNKI, school libraries and other Internet resources, and analyze our own actual situation.

1.3.2 Comparative contrast

By analyzing, summarizing and innovating on the experience of developed countries, we try to come up with a new path of urban-rural integration suitable for China's development; then make feasible recommendations for them according to the actual realities in China; Finally, the results are summarized and concluded.

1.3.3 Combining theory and practice

This paper, on the one hand, actively pays attention to relevant national policies. On the other hand, through different channels and aspects, data collection, the rural land system under the background of rural revitalization in China is comprehensively analyzed and compared, drawing on its successful experience, and putting forward

feasible suggestions for reference, thus helping to implement countermeasures, improvement measures as an organic unity, so as to promote the development of China's modern economic construction, which is also of great significance.

2. Changes in the Reform of the Rural Land System

2.1 Historical Evolution of Rural Land System Reform

The history of China's rural land system reform can be traced back to the 50s of the 20th century, when it was the period of the people's communalization movement^[6]. This phase was based mainly on collective ownership. After the Reform and Opening up, with the establishment and improvement of the socialist market economy, the expansion of agricultural industry, and the increase of farmer's income, a large number of new kind of problems and contradictions have emerged: First, a large number of agricultural farming land has been converted to non-farming land; Second, some local governments have contracted the management rights of rural land to individuals or organizations; Third, some illegal appropriation of state property has also increased, resulting in an intensification of violations of law and discipline.

China's rural land system has undergone a long and tortuous course of development, from 1950 to the Reform and Opening up, and the reform work entered the deep water zone. For over 30 years, China has made some remarkable achievements in reform. Looking back at the reform process, it can be divided into three stages: The first stage was the exploration and development of China's rural land system, which was from 1982 to 1993; The second stage was land reform rehabilitation and reconstruction, which was from 1994 till 2007; The third stage is rural land property rights system reform, which is from 2008 to the present.

China's rural land system reform has gone through three different stages: The first is land reform pilot projects, which was from 1987 to 2007; the second stage was the "regional household system separation" on a trial basis and the conversion of agriculture to non-agricultural areas. The third stage was since the Reform and Opening up which has continued to deepen and advance.

2.2 Main Features of Rural Land System Reform

From 1987 to the present, the main goal of rural land reform has been to increase farmer income. China's rural land system reform is divided into two stages.^[7] The first period started in the 1980s. This historical process has roughly gone through three basic models: the "household joint production contract responsibility system" and the reform of the "People's Commune Law", as well as the gradual implementation of collective ownership and cooperative operation of communes after the Reform and Opening up. The second stage has been continuously deepened from 1987 to 2003, mainly reflected in the basic characteristics of rural land system reform, and its development process also has the following four main characteristics:

With farmers' collective ownership as the main body, a variety of business modes coexist. China implements the household joint production contract responsibility system and the form of shareholding cooperative economic organization. Under this economic system, farmers and other producers and operators are in a holistic relationship; the cooperation mode of China's agricultural division of labor under the conditions of market economy provides a basic guarantee for the industrialization, mechanization and modernization of agriculture and animal husbandry in the modern sense. The structure of land property rights formed after the adjustment of the land system has also gradually changed from a single form to multiple forms, and the main content of the adjustment of the land system is on rural land, not just limited to agricultural production.

Adhering to people-oriented policy and overall planning. China is currently in the initial stage of socialism and the transition period of market economy; from the perspective of historical development, the transition from

planned economy to market economy, the transformation of extensive growth mode, and the continuous strengthening of traditional cultural concepts have provided important guiding ideology for reform^[8]. From the perspective of realistic construction: on the one hand, with the improvement of social productivity and the increasing abundance of material wealth brought about by the acceleration of industrialization, the waste of land resources has become more and more serious, therefore, we must adhere to people-oriented policy and overall planning. On the other hand, the purpose of China's rural land system reform is to meet social needs through the rational allocation of land resources and improving land use efficiency and effectiveness. The adjustment of the rural land system has been carried out in an all-round way, and the land reform mode has been transformed into a joint-stock operation mode.

2.3 The Historical Evolution and the Role of Rural Land System Reform

Therefore, in the background of rural revitalization, the reform of rural land system has the following characteristics:

Proposal and implementation of the urban-rural integrated development strategy. China is a big agricultural country, yet not a resource powerhouse. With the continuous advancement of the economy and society, the acceleration of the urbanization process, and the increasing number of problems in the process of industrialization, which has led to the increasing loss of confidence in the land by farmers, etc., the government has begun to think about how to achieve integrated urban and rural planning and construction by improving the land use structure. At the same time, the reform of rural land system in the background of rural revitalization also has its own particularities: first, it emphasizes the concept of people-oriented policy and ecological civilization. The reform of the land system has created more wealth not only for farmers, but for the state and the government as well, and in China's rural development, land resources scarcity and low land utilization rate have also seriously restricted the integration of urban and rural construction. Therefore, we must start land reform in the current background of rural revitalization.

Guaranteeing the balanced relationship between the right to survival of the weak and the right to realize benefits. With the rapid advance of social economy and the continuous improvement of urbanization, people's quality of life requirements are getting higher and higher; at the same time, due to the relatively low and unstable income of farmers, under the background of land system reform, farmers also have higher requirements for their own income and expenditure.

It is conducive to the realization of sustainable rural social and economic development. China is currently in the stage of accelerating urbanization, the continuous growth of urban population and the improvement of urbanization level have caused a large number of rural laborers to pour into the central area and gradually migrate to the city and thus drive the rapid growth of the local regional economy; At the same time, due to a series of influencing factors such as the dual structure of urban and rural areas, which have been seriously restricting the transfer of rural surplus labor force and the improvement of farmers' efficiency in land resource allocation, China's current sustainable social and economic development is facing many difficulties.

2.4 The Impact of Rural Land System Reform on Rural Revitalization

The purpose of land system reform is to transfer rural surplus labor to cities in order to achieve sustainable socio-economic development. Rural revitalization is a new urbanization construction model proposed and implemented by China in the new era according to its own national conditions. It requires promoting farmers' income by transforming land use patterns, optimizing allocation structures, and coordinating urban and rural spatial layout. Its core contents are: The first is to adhere to the concept of economical and intensive land use; The second is to

strictly control the approval procedures for rural land acquisition; The third is to achieve strict compensation standards for land acquisition, unified determination of compensation rates and the establishment of a reasonable price mechanism, and also to accomplish the "three certificates" work, so as to better and faster achieve the optimal allocation of land resources.

After the founding of the People's Republic of China, a large number of surplus labor in China's rural areas shifted to the cities to find employment and development; Due to the lack of a scientific and effective management system and the lack of protection of farmers' interests, some villagers and the government have simply mobilized rather than made voluntary efforts to solve these problems. Therefore, the reform of the rural land system is to realize China's socio-economic development and the improvement of farmers' living standards under the background of rural revitalization, which has a profound and far-reaching impact on the economic, political and cultural construction of rural areas.

3. Current Status and Existing Problems of Rural Land System Reform in the background of Rural Revitalization

3.1 Basic Situation of Rural Land System Reform

In China's rural areas, the "three certificates" mainly refer to the land contracting rights of farmer households, but due to historical, geographical and other reasons, the process of reform of the farmland system has been rather slow. In fact, China is currently in a period of economic transition. With the acceleration of social development and urbanization, the national policy orientation is gradually tilted towards rural areas. Therefore, it is imperative to reform China's current agricultural land system; At the same time, it is also necessary to take the relationship between China's national conditions and the dual structure of urban and rural areas into account, and when promoting the reform of the rural land system, it is also necessary to take into account that the deterioration of the living conditions of Chinese farmers and the increase in agricultural production costs have seriously affected the process of China's social and economic development.

The "three certificates" refer to rural land contracts, certificates of collective operation construction land use rights and land use planning permits, all of which belong to the basic rights of farmers, which are not only related to farmers' production rights and interests, but also affect social and economic development. Therefore, in order to truly realize rural revitalization, it is necessary to reform the farmland system.

3.2 Contradictions Encountered in the Reform of the Rural Land System

In the reform of the rural land system, there are situations that are incompatible with the development of the socialist market economy, which are mainly manifested as followed:

First, the land circulation policy is not perfect. At present, a unified, standard, complete and operable legal document that complies with national laws and regulations and social infrastructure planning has not been issued to clearly define the role of farmers' collective ownership in their families and what responsibilities they should bear; Secondly, in the reform of the rural land property rights system, there are situations where the interests of this special group, "agriculture", are neglected by focusing on urban development.

Second, the price of land circulation is various. In China, the reform of the land management system is mainly carried out through administrative means, and this has become the most important and critical link in the process of land property rights transfer. Factors like the acceleration of urbanization, the increase in demand for rural construction land, and the formulation and improvement of relevant laws and regulations have gradually promoted the establishment of a market-oriented mechanism for the circulation of homestead use rights by the government.

From the current national conditions of China, the reform of the land system in the background of rural revitalization has certain feasibility: first, effective management through administrative means, and bringing land property rights into the integrated urban and rural development system; The second is to regulate the circulation price of rural homestead use rights through legal means to ensure that its land system reform can really play a role in the background of rural revitalization; The third is to protect the rights and interests of farmers through legislation.

In China, the reform of the land system is mainly carried out through administrative means, however, rural land property rights as a civil right and property right have attracted the attention of many scholars. Therefore, it is particularly important to manage and utilize it rationally and effectively.

3.3 Ideas and Predicament for the Reform and Improvement of the Rural Land System

By analyzing the current rural land system reform and improvement ideas in China, we believe that in the background of rural revitalization, it is necessary to achieve national policy goals, adhere to fundamental principles and deepen the reform of the administrative system.

Under current land property rights system, the "Sannong (Agriculture, village, farmers) problem has not been well resolved. The main reasons are farmers' distrust of the land and fear of more conflicts in the country; Secondly, the irrationality of the rural collective property rights system has led to a large amount of social capital entering the cities and rural areas of developing countries, and these areas lack sufficient strength to support their large-scale expansion, which also restricts the reform and improvement of the rural land system. Therefore, under the current land property rights system, it is of great significance to implement appropriate scale management of agricultural land and achieve the national macro-control goals.

4. Ideas for Rural Land System Reform in the Background of Rural Revitalization

4.1 Overall Framework for Rural Land System Reform

In order to better realize the reform of the rural land system, we should continue to sum up and draw lessons and gradually improve current legal system of land property rights. Under the current background of the socialist market economy, rural economic development is facing a new round of profound changes and challenges. Therefore, the existing relevant theories need to be supplemented and amended accordingly; At the same time, we should adhere to the people-oriented concept as the guiding ideology to formulate policies and measures that meet the requirements of modern social development and can effectively promote the sustainable increase of farmers' income; It is also necessary to establish and improve the land circulation market mechanism, standardize land trade, and promote the continuous advancement of China's agricultural modernization process.

In the current land system reform in our country, we must constantly adjust and improve relevant laws and policies in accordance with the current reality of rural economic development and the goal of agricultural modernization in the new period of socialism. At the same time, we must also primarily protect the interests of farmers and comprehensively promote the strategy of governing the country according to law. We must protect the legitimate rights and interests of the broad masses of people from being infringed upon or trampled on via legislation, actively promoting the construction of a grassroots level democratic political work system and strengthening grassroots democratic autonomy can effectively promote the successful completion of China's rural revitalization and social stability, harmony and sustainable development.

Improving the land system and promoting the smooth implementation of China's Rural Revitalization strategy. We should see rural construction as an opportunity to continuously innovate and develop agricultural modernization; Measures such as strengthening the construction of the grassroots democratic self-government

work system and improving the participation of villagers in decision-making process can help to promote the smooth completion of China's rural revitalization process: the establishment and improvement of an effective, smooth, scientific and reasonable mechanism for making village affairs public, enhancing the ability of the masses to supervise the implementation of government policies, and improving the village officials election system all require corresponding reforms.

Deepening the reform of the land system management is an important measure not only to promote the healthy and sustainable development of rural economy and society, but also improve the living standards of farmers as well, and it is also a necessary measure to solve the problem of rural land system and promote the smooth implementation of Rural Revitalization strategy.

4.2 Rural Land System Reform Path under the background of Rural Revitalization

In the background of rural revitalization, we must adhere to the improvement and innovation of the land system as the core, and continuously promote the reform and development of the rural land property rights system and the collective asset appraisal mechanism. At the same time, considerable attention should also be paid to strengthening the protection of farmers' legitimate rights and interests. Through a series of policies and regulations, we can guide the villagers to actively participate in the construction of a new socialist countryside.

First of all, the leading role of the government should be strengthened: On the one hand, establish and improve the relevant legal and regulatory system; On the other hand, give full play to the basic position and link role of the market in resource allocation, promote the reform and development process of land circulation system and collective land property rights, and push forward the improvement and development of rural land system. Then we should establish and improve the relevant legal and regulatory system to provide strong support for rural revitalization: First, legislation and clearly define farmers' contractual business rights and collective property rights should be further strengthened; Second the legitimate interests of farmers should be to protect by formulating corresponding norms and policies; Third, we should rationally allocate and integrate and utilize under the existing land property rights distribution mechanism to ensure the smooth completion of new socialist rural construction and the realization of the task goals.

4.3 Land System and Methods in the Background of Rural Revitalization

In the background of rural revitalization, in order to accelerate the process of rural land system reform, we should promote China's economic development and the improvement of farmers' living standards, as well as social stability and harmony in the new era. This can be done from the following aspects: The first to actively guide governments and departments at all levels to formulate land property rights distribution plans that meet their actual conditions; The second is to regulate and restrict it through relevant provisions such as laws and regulations. Through the above measures, we can make the subject, object and content of the land system more clear, and at the same time strictly manage and supervise it. In addition, when improving land title distribution plan, attention should be paid to the following points: First, the issue of agricultural land ownership should be the primary consideration. Because it concerns the fundamental interests of farmers and the future development of the country; The second is to establish and improve the institutions of rural collective ownership economic organizations and property rights ownership systems, and regulate and restrict them through laws and regulations; The third is to establish and improve power management system on rural collective land regulated by laws and regulations; The fourth is to improve the land contracting dispute resolution mechanism.

5. Discussion on Rural Land System Reform in the Background of Rural Revitalization

5.1 Improve the policy system for rural land system reform

In the background of rural land system reform, we should put forward new ideas for the current Rural Revitalization strategy, and build a systematic, professional and standardized agricultural land property rights system that is complete, reasonable, orderly and sustainable.

First of all, it is necessary to establish and improve relevant laws and regulations and to safeguard farmers' rights and interests from infringement by formulating and harmonizing supporting guidelines that are consistent with the implementation of the Constitution of the People's Republic of China; Secondly, it is necessary to accelerate the pace of rural land system reform and legal system construction, and clarify various specific measures and procedural provisions at the legislative level; Then, it is necessary to build a unified, complete, comprehensive and practical rural revitalization policy framework system to solve the inconsistency, incoordination and unsustainability of the land policy; Finally, it is necessary to improve the relevant laws and regulations of rural revitalization to provide a solid and reliable institutional guarantee for rural revitalization.

5.2 Rural land market demand under the background of rural revitalization

The rural land property rights system should be improved. First of all, it is necessary to clarify the main position of the landowner. In China, as a vulnerable group, the interests of farmers are the most in need of protection, so they must be given the corresponding legal rights and interests in property rights and property use rights through legal forms; The second, it is imperative to establish and improve relevant legislative work, regulate the circulation of agricultural land and relevant dispute resolution mechanisms, etc.; Finally, it is vital to fundamentally change the problem of unrecognition, irrationality and even illegality of the "three sessions" system in collective economic organizations. In concrete implementation, we must adhere to the concept of "governing the country according to law", establish and improve the management system of rural land property rights, and strengthen the protection of farmers' land rights.

In the process of land transfer, farmers and operators will have some problems, such as the lack of recognition of the status of the main body, and the lack of business ideas and legal awareness. To solve these problems, it is necessary to improve and deepen the institutional mechanism of rural land property rights management through institutional innovation; the guiding role of government must be strengthened; We should also establish and improve relevant laws and regulations, and carry out standardized reforms to protect the interests of landowners as the core ideological starting point.

Market demand. In China, land is a scarce resource, but with the continuous development of society, its use and value have also changed. This requires us to establish a complete, fair and reasonable land property rights system; the relationship between the collective economic organization and the family should be clearly defined by legal form.

5.3 Institutional innovation

Family relations should be clearly defined through legal forms and properly handled during the transfer of land. Market demand. China's Rural Revitalization strategy is to "develop and strengthen the new socialist countryside" and achieve the goal of building a moderately prosperous society in an all-round way, put forward and implemented under the common demand of the new era of the overall framework concept of new urban and rural areas with Chinese characteristics (Document No. 1 of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China), and build a harmonious and beautiful countryside as the ultimate goal, research and formulate a series of policies and measures, so as to promote the sustainable increase of farmers' income, the continuous advancement of

agricultural modernization, etc., accelerate the healthy and orderly development of China's economy and urbanization.

In innovating rural land system, we must adhere to "adapting measures to local conditions" and carry out specific implementation according to the different development conditions and characteristics of various places. For example, we can improve cultivated land protection policies and cultivated land circulation systems. At the same time, we can also increase investment in rural infrastructure construction and social undertakings; A series of related measures, such as establishing and improving the agricultural science and technology extension system and service mechanism, can promote the sustainable increase of farmers' income and the transformation of rural economic growth mode in the new era; In the process of confirming land rights, it is necessary to achieve equal rights as the goal, and respect the wishes of villagers to choose the scope of applicable land.

6. Conclusion

A sound rural land property rights system must be establish. There are still many problems in confirming land rights, First of all, due to the imperfect legal and regulatory system, the management system and procedures are not mature enough, resulting in farmers' poor understanding of relevant policies; Secondly, some local governments neglect policy implementation in order to pursue political performance; Finally, in order to seek personal interests, some officials will "privately approved use of land", resulting in a reduction in farming land or even barely making living.

The establishment of a sound rural land property rights system can not only promote the intensive and scientific management of rural land, but also effectively increase farming land, grain production and farmers' income. Therefore, we must adhere to the concept of "people-oriented" in the process of deepening reform. At the same time, we must adhere to the concept of "governing the country according to law" and improve the management mechanism of rural land property rights. In the process of advancing, we must adhere to the concept of "governing the country by law", establish and improve the land property rights management system, and strengthen the construction of land circulation mechanisms. At the same time, we must adhere to the concept of "governing the country according to law", establish and improve the rural land property rights management system, and strengthen the protection of farmers' land rights.

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